

Appendix B: Oxygen UV emission model

Appendix B.1: Optical depth and extinction calculation

In this study, we modeled Ganymede's auroral emissions by considering the five spectral transitions responsible for the oxygen emission lines at 130.4 and 135.6 nm (see table 2). We also accounted for the contribution of solar irradiation and reflection of the solar continuum by the surface. To compute the radiative transfer, we adapted the solver to our context. The optical depth $\tau(z, \nu)$ is given by:

$$\tau(z, \nu) = \int_z^\infty \kappa_u(z', \nu) dz', \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where $\kappa_u(z, \nu)$ is the total extinction coefficient for each transition u considered (with $u = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$), defined as:

$$\kappa_u(z, \nu) = \frac{h\nu}{4\pi} (n_l(z)B_{lu} - \alpha n_u(z)B_{ul}) \phi(\nu - \nu_0, z) + \sum_i n_i(z) [\sigma_{\text{abs}}^i + \sigma_{\text{diff}}^i], \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where n_i , σ_{abs}^i and σ_{diff}^i represent respectively the density [cm^{-3}], the absorption cross section [cm^2], and the scattering cross section [cm^2] of species i , with $i = [\text{O}, \text{O}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{H}_2, \text{H}]$. n_u is the density of O^* in the excited (upper) state u , and n_l is the density of O in the (lower) state l , which is also the ground state, with:

$$n_u = \frac{\eta}{A_{ul}} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

and

$$n_l = n_{\text{O}} - n_u \frac{g_u}{\sum_{u'} g_{u'}} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

B_{lu} and B_{ul} (Mihalas and Hubeny 2015) are respectively the stimulated excitation coefficient [$\text{kg}^{-1} \text{s}$] and the stimulated emission coefficient given by, respectively:

$$B_{lu} = \frac{g_u}{g_l} B_{ul} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

and

$$B_{ul} = A_{ul} \frac{c^2}{2h\nu_{ul}^3} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

α is a multiplicative factor accounting for the coupling between emission and reabsorption transitions from and to state u and defined by:

$$\alpha = \frac{B_{ul}}{\sum_{u'} B_{u'l}} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

This factor is defined for each excited state of atomic oxygen, $^3\text{S}^0$ and $^5\text{S}^0$, considered in this study. $\phi(\nu - \nu_0, z)$ is the Voigt profile for each spectral line centered on frequency ν_0 considered in this study.

In this study, we only considered scattering by atomic oxygen and the scattering cross-sections σ_{diff}^O were taken from Barthélemy et al. (2004) and are specific to each upper state u of atomic oxygen included in the model. To compute the reflection of the solar continuum by Ganymede's surface, the total extinction in the wavelength ranges near and away from the emission line frequencies is given by:

$$\kappa(z, \nu) = \sum_i n_i \sigma_{\text{abs}}^i. \quad (\text{B.8})$$

The photoabsorption cross-sections used in our model come primarily from a photochemical model developed for Titan (Dobrijevic et al. 2016) and Triton (Benne et al. 2024). Several files are sourced from the Leiden database¹. For atomic H, we used data from Palenius et al. (1976) and Heays et al. (2017). For H_2O , data are from Yoshino et al. (1996), with branching ratios from Mordaunt et al. (1993); Stief (1974); Slanger & Black (1982), and Heays et al. (2017). For O and O_2 , we used data from the Leiden database and the references are given in the database for each file. All datasets were interpolated to match the spectral grid of our model.

Appendix B.2: Internal source function calculation

We then computed the internal source function $S_u(\tau, \nu)$, inspired by the works of Gladstone (1992) and Barthélemy et al. (2004), and defined by the following expression:

$$S_u(\tau, \nu) = \frac{j_u(\tau, \nu)}{\kappa_u(z, \nu)}, \quad (\text{B.9})$$

where $j_u(\tau, \nu)$ is the emission function associated with a transition from the upper state u , accounting for both the internal emission of the atmosphere and the frequency redistribution. This emission function is given by the following expression:

$$j_u(\tau, \nu) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \eta(\tau) \frac{A_{ul}}{\sum_{u'} A_{u'l}} \phi(\nu - \nu_0) + \frac{\tilde{\omega}}{4\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \sigma_{\text{diff}}^u(\tau, \nu') r(\tau, \nu, \nu') \pi I_0(\nu') e^{-\tau(\nu')} d\nu' + \tilde{\omega} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-1}^{+1} \sigma_{\text{diff}}^u(\tau, \nu, \nu') u(\tau, \nu', \mu') d\mu' d\nu', \quad (\text{B.10})$$

where $\eta(\tau)$ is the production rate of O^* in the $^3\text{S}^0$ and $^5\text{S}^0$ states, $\tilde{\omega}$ is the scattering albedo of the transition, i.e., the fraction of de-excitations from the upper state u returning directly to the ground state l rather than to an intermediate level. $r(\tau, \nu, \nu')$ is the frequency redistribution function, which characterizes the probability that a photon absorbed at a given frequency is re-emitted at a different frequency, capturing effects like Doppler shifts, natural broadening, and partial coherence in scattering events. In this study, we used the angle-averaged partial redistribution (AAPR) function R_{II} (Hubeny & Mihalas 2014), as in Gladstone (1992).

Since the third term in the function $j_u(\tau, \nu)$ depends on the mean radiation field, and therefore on the specific intensity $u(\tau, \mu, \phi)$. We modeled the emissions associated with the different transitions considered in our radiative transfer model through an iterative process until the source function $S(\tau, \nu)$ converged, before computing the final emission spectrum.

Appendix B.3: Model validation

To validate our radiative transfer model, we implemented several verification steps. First, we tested our atomic oxygen emission model by comparing it with laboratory measurements of

¹ https://home.strw.leidenuniv.nl/~ewine/photo/by_atom_molecule.html

the 130.4 nm triplet, obtained with very high spectral resolution (~ 0.05 nm) in the experiment of Makarov et al. (2004). In this experiment, H_2O molecules were bombarded by a 100 eV electron beam, producing characteristic UV emissions from atomic oxygen. To reproduce this experimental setup using our modeling chain (TransPlanet coupled with the atomic oxygen UV emission model), we simulated the precipitation of a monoenergetic 100 eV electron beam into a pure H_2O atmosphere. The emissions of the triplet lines at 130.22, 130.49, and 130.60 nm were modeled and compared with the experimental spectra, as shown in Fig. B.1. However, due to the lack of cross-section data for the interaction $e^- + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2 + \text{O}^*(^5S) + e^-$, we were unable to reproduce the 135.56 and 135.85 nm doublet emissions also measured by Makarov et al. (2004).

Fig. B.1: Comparison between the simulated spectrum of the O I triplet at 130.22, 130.49, and 130.60 nm (in red), obtained by modeling the precipitation of 100 eV monoenergetic electrons into a pure H_2O atmosphere, and the laboratory spectrum of Makarov et al. (2004) experiment (in black), measured with a spectral resolution of 0.05 nm.

In a second step, we compared our model to the study by de Kleer et al. (2023), who simulated the O I line ratio $I(135.6 \text{ nm})/I(130.4 \text{ nm})$ for Ganymede to constrain the atmospheric composition. Their model considers several extreme cases of atmospheres dominated by O_2 , H_2O , or O. We reproduced their methodology by simulating the line ratio for the O_2 and O cases (H_2O was excluded due to insufficient cross-section data), but using the more updated atmospheric model from Vorburger et al. (2024). For 100 eV monoenergetic electron precipitation, we obtained line ratio values of 0.021 for O and 2.21 for O_2 , compared to the values of 0.022 and 2.2 reported by de Kleer et al. (2023). This confirms the consistency of our atomic oxygen emission model.

Finally, we compared our radiative transfer model with that of Gladstone (1992) by modeling the atomic oxygen emission lines at 130.4 nm and 135.6 nm, using the same atmospheric structure and the same outputs from the electron transport model. The differences obtained in the total brightness of the simulated lines after radiative transfer remained below 3%, confirming the numerical reliability of our approach.

Frequency redistribution in non-LTE radiative transfer is essential to describe resonant lines and scattering. However, in the case of Ganymede, the low density of the main scatterer renders these effects negligible in integrated spectra. We therefore chose to neglect this term to accelerate computations, without significant loss of accuracy.

Lastly, the solar spectrum used in our simulations is based on high-resolution observations from Curdt et al. (2001, 2004), rescaled to match a solar minimum activity phase consistent with the Juno/UVS observation dates of the PJ34. This configuration allows for accurate modeling of the solar continuum reflected from Ganymede's surface without further temporal adjustments.

Appendix E: Spectral fitting of auroral emissions across all analyzed regions

Fig. E.1 presents the average UV emission spectra observed in each of the 17 sunlit auroral subregions defined in our study (see Fig. 1). The characteristic oxygen lines around 130.4 nm and 135.6 nm are clearly visible, with varying intensities across regions. These fits illustrate the ability of our model to accurately reproduce the observed auroral spectra and to constrain the properties of the precipitating electrons in Ganymede's atmosphere.

These observed spectra were extracted from the UVS data cubes of the *Juno* PJ34 by integrating the photon counts measured in each region and averaging them at each wavelength to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N). The main atomic oxygen emission lines centered around 130.4 nm and 135.6 nm are clearly visible in most regions, with line intensities and intensity ratios varying significantly depending on location. These variations reflect differences in auroral brightness and suggest locally varying conditions in terms of atmospheric composition, electron precipitation, and solar zenith angle.

The blue, red, and green curves overplotted on the observed spectra (in gray) correspond to the best fits obtained from our coupled model (TransPlanet + radiative transfer model for atomic oxygen UV emission), assuming either a monoenergetic, a Maxwellian or a kappa distribution of precipitating electrons, respectively. For each region, the synthetic spectrum corresponds to the pair of parameters [$\langle E \rangle$, ψ] that maximizes the likelihood function $P(\langle E \rangle, \psi)$ over the explored grid (see Sect. 4). These fits allow us to accurately reproduce both the overall spectral shape and the relative line intensities, thus validating the model's ability to constrain the properties of the precipitating electrons from observed UV auroral spectra.

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Fig. E.1: Average UV emission spectra measured by Juno/UVS in the 17 sunlit auroral subregions of Ganymede considered in this study (see Fig.1). The observed spectra, averaged within each region to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio, are shown in gray. The blue, red, and green curves represent the best-fit synthetic spectra obtained from our coupled model (TransPlanet + atomic oxygen UV emission model). The estimated parameter pairs $[\langle E \rangle, \psi]$ that maximize the likelihood $P(\langle E \rangle, \psi)$ in the explored grid (see Sect. 4), are shown in legend, for a monoenergetic distribution case, a Maxwellian distribution case, and a kappa distribution case of the precipitated electrons in the model, respectively.